

BRCA1

CCNE1

DHFR_AA489055

DHFR_R01547

E2F1_H61303

PCNA_H13004

RRM1

CCNE2

CDC25A_AA071514

CDC28/cdc2

CDC6

DHFR_N52980

DMTF1

E2F1_AA424950

HDAC3_AA973283

MCM2

PCNA_AA450264

RRM2_AA187351

TYMS

CDC25A_AA913262

CDC25A_R09063

RRM2_AA826373

CKS1_AA278629

CDC2

CDC2_AA278152

BIRC5

BUB1B

BUB3

BUB3_AA405955

CCNB2

CCND1(PRAD1)_AA487700

CCNF

CDC25C

CDC27

CDKN1B(p27.Kip1)

CDKN3

CENPA

CENPF

CKS1

CKS1_N53308

CKS2_AA010065

CKS2_AA292964

STK15_H63492

STK15_R19158

CCNB1

CDC20

CDC27_T81764

CDC28/cdc2_T77758

PLK

BUB1

CCNA2

CDC25B_AA448659

CDC25B_H14392

E2F5

NASP

MCM6_AA663995

SLBP

MCM6_AA976533

MCM6_N59689

MSH2_AA219061

MSH2_AI792246

CDKN2C

HDAC3_H88588

NUCKS

NUCKS_AI053436

NUCKS_AA927182

